

Significance of Oldowan in the Lower Paleolithic Period

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Abstract

*The Oldowan industry, characterized by its simple yet effective stone tools, represents a crucial milestone in human evolutionary history. This paper explores the significance of Oldowan technology within the Lower Paleolithic period, highlighting its role in early hominin behavior, cognitive development, and adaptive strategies. Originating approximately 2.6 million years ago, Oldowan tools—comprising primarily choppers, flakes, and cores—mark the advent of systematic stone tool production. These artifacts provide insights into the subsistence practices and ecological interactions of early hominins, revealing a shift towards increased meat consumption and resource exploitation. The emergence of Oldowan technology is closely associated with *Homo habilis*, underscoring a pivotal point in the evolutionary trajectory towards more complex tool-making and cognitive abilities. Through a comprehensive review of archaeological findings, this study underscores the Oldowan's transformative impact on early human societies, laying the foundation for subsequent technological advancements and cultural evolution.*

Keywords

Oldowan tools; Lower Paleolithic; *Homo habilis*; stone tool technology; human evolution

Oldowan in the Lower Paleolithic period, simple stone tools dating back to 2.6 million years ago, the expression that best explains the purpose of this stone tool and the idea behind its construction is that they were created by taking our molars as an example, and even in the period when agriculture began, stones for grinding wheat to grind plants or animal meat must have been inspired by our molars, which are our grinding teeth, in my opinion.

The Acheulean Acheulean stone tool from the lower paleolithic period dating back to 1.3 million years ago, which is now depicted as a hand axe, was modeled after the dens caninus teeth, and I think it has functions such as shredding meat, processing skin, and digging the soil. Before these, the tooth-jaw bones of animals may have been used for these processes. They may have made a connection between human bones and stone-rock; human and animal bones are at least as durable as stones and rocks. These stone tools may be older than the year they were dated.

You can cut lava flowing from a volcano into shapes. This is how you get blocks of rock.

2.) It is now accepted by the scientific community that humans and chimpanzees evolved from a common ancestor. Chimpanzees and other apes and gorillas live in trees and forests. The most commonly consumed food is tree fruits. So I thought there must be something that distinguishes tree fruits from animal and plant foods. There are poisonous plants, poisonous mushrooms, poisonous animals, but are there poisonous fruits? No. If you eat a grass and it is poisonous, it can kill you. It is

difficult to distinguish because there are so many alternatives in herbs. It is easier to be a carnivore and more difficult to be a herbivore in this respect. While there are a certain number of non-poisonous animals in nature, it is more difficult to keep in mind both the species and the poisonousness of the herbs and to pass them on from generation to generation. If human beings could survive in water rather than on land, they would look younger and live longer. It would be more beneficial for the plant if it grows in water or on land. According to the observations I have made, I think that the watery environment is more beneficial for the development and growth of plants than land. The bag full of wheat or the earthen cube in your hand will germinate the wheat with the moisture that enters it after a while. Moisture and water mean life. According to my observations, the roots of the onion plant that we try to grow in water have an unusual length and after a while, the roots of the onion plant are observed to intertwine with each other and form a winding relationship, they try to hold on to each other, just like the stem of the ivy plant. So this is the overgrowth of the roots of the onion plant growing in water and the roots cling to each other and protect themselves in this way.

It will tell us something about the evolution of the roots of plants. If the plant's ancestor existed in a wetland environment, we would expect that in future generations the roots of the plant would be more intertwined with each other.

3.) We sleep by concentrating on one point, with our eyes closed of course. If something sudden happens to break this focus, you can't fall asleep and you jump out of your bed, what is known in science as a fall. This is how I explain it, "focusing on a point". I think I have brought a new theory to the world of science. When you focus on one point, it becomes easier to sleep, people seem to think of one thing when they are awake, but when we are awake, different parts of our brain work simultaneously. This needs to be millimilized so that you can achieve the calmness necessary to fall asleep. In times of stress, you don't feel sleepy and you can't sleep, or you can't sleep when your life is in danger. Your brain focuses on trying to cope with the stress and your brain is working and producing more information than usual. This makes it difficult to sleep. You know hypnosis. You are asked to focus on a point. In hypnosis experiments, which are mostly done on rabbits and chickens, all the attention is focused on

the rabbit and the rabbit is made to focus only on your eyes. The rabbit is hypnotized in this way and remains motionless for a certain period of time and sleeps with its eyes open for a while. I guess this can have negative effects on both humans and animals. We go to places we have never seen before, or we can talk to a deceased relative as if they had never died, we can eat in our dreams. Is our life divided into what should be and what is?

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"Or why don't we see ourselves hunting buffalo with a bow and arrow in our dreams?" That's my question, and sometimes a question helps us explain past scientific realities. If information can be transferred genetically, some people argue this.

4.) Bird eggs, or specifically chicken eggs, appear as a form of self-reproduction and self-sufficiency with the ability and capacity to continue the generation. A chick emerges from the yellow part of the egg and grows and develops by eating the white of the egg. The chick embryo inside the egg shell develops. I observed whether these plants also have it. For example, if a tomato that has reached sufficient maturity has not been plucked from its branch by humans and is still standing on its branch, its seeds grow and sprout by consuming the water and vitamins in the plant. When it reaches the required maturity, the skin of the tomato becomes thinner and in order for the tomato sprout to fall to the ground, the embryo inside the tomato puts pressure on the skin of the tomato and comes out by piercing the shell. . In fact, even if you do not take the tomato seed and bury it in the ground, the tomato is programmed to grow its own embryo (its own tomato sprout) within itself for the continuation of its own generation, in accordance with the laws of nature. While this was the case in prehistoric times,

today people are more impatient and have disrupted the order of nature in order to have more tomatoes. This also applies to watermelon, cucumber, strawberry, apricot and other vegetables and fruits.

Voice recognition: Even though some people's voices sound similar, they are different from each other. We recognize the people we love by their voices, and we even recognize the people we dislike. This also applies to animals, of course. For example, lions recognize the voices of members of their own pride. For example, a lioness who catches prey calls her cubs from afar and calls them to herself. She does this not just by saying certain things. Lion cubs can tell whether the lion they do not see is their mother or not by the color of the mother lion's voice. Lion cubs take action when they hear the tone they are used to.

5.) Mitosis was the first evolutionary process in which the ancestral cell of the human cell underwent mitosis, and we know that humans were immortal during this period. These ancestral cells must have interacted with cells belonging to other living things with which they shared the same environment. There was no need for sex in this process. Meiosis is always a secondary principle of division, mitosis is more inclusive and older. Gender differences and the concept of sex certainly came into existence with the advent of meiosis. In the early evolutionary process, the humanoid cell became more complex and more systematic over time. Color pigments and algae in the water have been effective in the process of the existence of living things. Criteria such as skin color and gender emerge in line with the laws of physics and are genetically transmitted to the next generation. We know the effect of heat on sex. Skin color is a result of this kind of physics.

The crossover came later. Maybe there was only the male chromosome and it was mapping itself through mitosis and differentiating itself through meiosis, and then the female chromosome came and the crossover happened. The two parts of the human being are not completely symmetrical, you know. The frontal lobe has grown later, like it's swollen and cracked. It's possible to say that the frontal lobe developed later. The left lobe represents the right half of the human being and the right lobe represents the left half of the human being, and human beings, like all other living things, are composed of two symmetrical halves. Potatoes, wheat, fruit seeds are all made of two halves. It is not completely symmetrical, of course there are specific, slight nuance differences.

Do plants have sexes? Are there male roses, male onions, male lemons?

Why did meiosis arise? Was mitosis insufficient and that's why it emerged? Mitosis is an easier and more mass-productive form of division. If we were to divide by mitosis, we would not be able to fit on earth, we would reproduce very quickly.

Perhaps the first species to exist on earth was man. The first human cell emerged, the first primitive single-celled but very complex form of the first human being in today's sense could be the first systematic living species that emerged. What has meiosis done to human beings and animals, has it made it possible for them to make their own decisions about their own reproduction? And in mitosis, both sexes are present in a single living being and it is possible for plants or protozoa to be pollinated by bees, nectar birds, winged insects and the wind. So the existence of single-sex individuals in humans must have started with meiosis. Before that, male humans could also give birth. I think that the anal and vaginal opening was from a single point, and in the evolutionary process, the two started to occur from different openings. With the separation of the vaginal and anal opening, the existence of two different sexes becomes more evident. When you look at many animals in nature, anal and vaginal openings function from a single point. This is a theory that confirms my thesis that the female sex has separated from the male. Ectopic pregnancy and false pregnancy are sometimes possible in women, but is there such a thing as false ovulation? Is it possible to have a fake menstrual period that is not productive? What weaknesses emerged as the male and female sexes diverged? You must be familiar with the

concepts of "your blood, your descendants", what is meant by blood here? Could it be menstrual blood? In the evolutionary process, when sex was divided into two parts, male and female, menstrual blood was passed from the male to the female. As it is known, in today's primitive tribes, intra-clan marriages are common and marriages from outside the tribe are not possible.

This is a situation related to men's desire to continue their lineage. For humans, the continuation of the male lineage has been a priority at all times in the evolutionary process. Among the Jews, it is said that such a woman continues the lineage, and a Jewish man is not asked to marry a woman of another religion. Woman is the only living creature that can continue the lineage of men in the evolutionary process that gave them feminine characteristics.

One society consisted of individuals who used only their right hands, while the other tribe used their left hands in primitive societies. As a result of their interaction with each other, this separation has now disappeared.

How could this distinction between right and left have happened in the evolutionary process. How did man, when he was still in the form of a systematic cell, map himself into two halves, right and left, to give himself the form he has today? First, the left lobe mapped itself and the right lobe was formed. The brain first mapped itself into right and left, and then continued to do so in a systematic way, resulting in a form close to its present appearance. This may have been the process that led a systematic cell to the human form of today. Humans used to express their emotions with facial expressions like other animals. Today's modern humans exaggerate their emotions and share them with their close and distant surroundings both vocally, mimically and behaviorally. It is natural and natural to endure events that affect us emotionally and to be patient. This is more obvious in plants. Were we like plants, that is, one half of them may be less developed than the other half depending on the water reaching them, or the side that sees the sun is more developed than the other side. In the first evolutionary process, man was a deformed creature like a potato tuber. When you look at a potato tuber, you see that it is made up of two symmetrical hemispheres, but one of these symmetrical hemispheres is sometimes less perfectly shaped than the other hemisphere. If it has limited access to nutrients, this prevents it from growing and maintaining its shape.

6.) There must be a different gravitational force emitted by subatomic particles. They cannot be attracted or repelled by each other.

While black holes are trying to push themselves to create space for themselves, to rub against other galaxies and the strong wavelengths they emit, and to move forward, we should not forget that a black hole may have more than one gravitational field in cases where one gravitational field is insufficient. Black holes exist as a reaction to something, and when it is lacking, they unite, join forces and defend against it. What is it that they are resisting? We must reveal this. Or, in case one black hole is insufficient, it is possible for more than one gravitational field to emerge. I think that the side with the largest area is the uppermost part of the black hole and is the easiest for us to observe. Because as the black hole moves inward, its area shrinks and its ability to absorb everything around it must weaken, in accordance with the laws of physics. In other words, the black hole pulls the star or planet to a certain point, breaks it apart, and then returns it to the universe.

That's probably what happened in the atom, just like the cell. There is a basic division principle and a differentiating principle of division such as meiosis, probably in atoms as well. It is already impossible for subatomic particles to be independent of each other.

What are the substances released in the atom when subatomic particles are produced and react and interact? There is no research on this yet.

I think there are rock plants, and we need to obtain concrete data by concretizing this in a laboratory environment. Rocks cannot be formed only as a result of natural events. We know that it is the type of fish that creates sea sand. So, did the soil layers on earth appear only as a result of natural events? Are there any plants that help erode the stones or rocks that play a role in the formation of soil and sand? There is no scientific data on this, but I think it is possible.

Gravity within the stone. When you divide a stone in half, you will see the magnetic effect and the two pieces attract each other.

7.) It is said in various articles that circumcision reduces sexual desire. No, it cannot be like this, it may shorten the duration of sexual intercourse, but a circumcised man enjoys sexuality more than an uncircumcised man, because by removing the upper skin, the nerves activate the sense of feeling, which increases the desire and pleasure of sexual intercourse. And in my opinion, being circumcised just once in a lifetime is not enough because the skin recovers and becomes more numb to external stimulation. This needs to be repeated at certain intervals throughout life. In some societies, the skin of the male reproductive organ may be thicker or thinner than in other societies, but the fact is that the skin on the male and female reproductive organs is very thick and as if it evolved from a leather sheath that protects the sexual organ. As in horses, dogs, birds. The same applies to your lips, and when your lip skin dries and flakes to renew itself, your lips keep the sensation of sensation at maximum.

Do plant leaves have skin?

When we examine the leaves of the willow tree, whose scientific name is *Salix*, you will see that there is an outer green leaf tissue surrounding the inner tissue that appears in green and small pieces around the veins of the leaf that resemble fish bones. This outermost green tissue, which continues uninterruptedly towards the tip of the leaf, is the leaf skin surrounding the leaf of the *Salix* plant. The green and small tissues surrounding the fishbone-shaped veins in the inner part of the leaf are protected by the outermost leaf skin that surrounds them, and this leaf skin gives the leaf its shape. This is the outermost leaf skin, which is in the form of jagged protrusions at the tips of the leaves of the *Salix* plant. Why is one white sugar used when fermenting yogurt? Or if we do not use white beet sugar while fermenting yogurt, then if you add enough beet sugar to the yogurt and mix it, you will see that the yogurt retains its durability for a very long time. While yogurt produces bacteria and spoils within minutes in a hot environment, yogurt with added sugar will not spoil for weeks. In order to preserve the durability of vegetables for a long time, white beet sugar is added to the pickles during fermentation with vinegar, and there are even pickled red beets. I think sugar is used to preserve food as a result of these observations. In living plants, for example, trees increase their sugar production in the fall to protect themselves from the cold. This protects the tree from the cold during the winter. An organ with a sensitive tissue like the brain has a considerable amount of sugar in its structure. As I said, we can say that sugar has a protective effect. We should not limit ourselves to this, but make other observations.

8.) Water swells when it gets hot, sea water swells when it gets hot. This should be valid for solid objects. I think this is possible for all solid objects, even if they do not expand as much as liquids. This will also be valid for gases, so when we think that gases will expand more than liquids, our atmosphere should swell and expand. How are clouds affected by this temperature change? Since the atmospheric layer exists, it can't be at the same level, right? Changes in the height of the atmosphere need to be followed. Is the atmosphere getting closer to the earth?

Rains and lightning must maintain the electrical balance between the clouds, the earth, and the oceans. When you hold a magnet to the ground, the soil accumulates around it and sticks to the magnet. The soil has magnetic properties, this is a slight magnetic effect. If your hair gets wet in the rain, it will frizz,

but if you wet your hair with water from the tap at home, your hair will not frizz. We can understand from this observation of mine whether rainwater carries more electrical charge or less electrical charge. 9.) In past civilizations what did God give to man, as a gift, as a blessing. Take this gold, my servant. Take this house, take this wheat. Take this lamb. Take this dress.

Others were born prophets. For example, when Jesus was born, he said, "I am a prophet. Even though his father, who was a prophet, had many sons, the fact that Joseph was chosen to be a prophet among the others is like the Ottoman sultanate being passed on to a child. Whichever son the father wants to be the prophet is chosen to be the prophet. It is possible to see prophets as god-kings.

When the Prophet was a child, his heart was cut open and he was washed, this is a statement that is found in semi-sacred Islamic sources, so he is portrayed as a holy person who was blessed and could not do evil or sin. In fact, it was obvious when he was a child, but why wait until the age of 40 for the first revelation. Is the arrival of orders and books a sign of prophethood?

Prophethood was revealed to Muhammad at the age of 40. Is the book or the commandment a sign of prophethood?

It is said that Jesus Christ will come back to earth and obey Muhammad, the Prophet of Islam. I think this is a deceptive discourse, I think it is just lies told by some Muslim scholars to get Christians to choose Islam as their religion. Because there is a thing in Islam that if it leads to a good result, then there is no harm in lying. An example of this is a lie told to make things right between a couple who are thinking of breaking up is not a sin from a religious point of view. I think the fact that Christians are the majority makes them, the Muslims, greedy, they want everyone, every Christian to obey them, the Muslims. There is also the race of my prophet is superior. Some Muslim scholars say that the most superior prophet and person is Muhammad, the prophet of Islam. This is not possible because in the Holy Book of Islam it says that one of you has no superiority over the other. It says that all human beings have equal rights.

10.) Nested letters and text. Numbers, punctuation marks and letters alone will no longer suffice for coding, software and encryption. So we need to renew and update the characters we encode and encrypt. Or we can overlap a number and a letter to get a new character. For example, we can make two nested zeros add up to form a new number. Or we can overlap two z's to form a new letter. This can increase the security and authenticity of our software and the characters we encrypt.

Materials that have been used for thousands of years to build houses and buildings need to be modernized. We need to start experimenting with new materials that are durable, flexible and allow multi-storey construction. Foldable buildings, foldable detached houses, walls that can be transparent at any time could be possible. There are some cities and some settlements where there is almost no green space, no plants. These places don't need night. To illuminate these places at night, artificial star balls can be placed on the clouds. This would be useful in rainy weather. For this we need artificial illuminators that can be suspended in the sky. Today, there are artificial wireless illuminators that can be suspended in the air for a short time, which are used to illuminate battlefields at night. This could be possible in the sky too. We should work on this.

11.) If you surround the animal and start throwing stones at the same time from a safe distance, you can kill the animal. It is very likely that animals were understood in this way in primitive societies. Later, they must have hunted by throwing stones at the animal with catapults or slingshots. This may also be the origin of punishing adulterers and murderers with stoning. This is how the punishment of stoning must have emerged.

First, the tribesmen gathered around a single fire, then they separated the fire and people gathered in groups around different fire clusters. Was there a god of fire? Were people making sacrifices to the fire?

Is the tradition of cremating the deceased a part of the sacrifice to the god of fire? In which geography did fire worship first appear?

As described in the sacred texts of Islam and the Holy Quran, the God-King in Mesopotamia has a huge pool of fire and Nimrod, the God-King, wants to throw Abraham into this fire with the help of a catapult.

In fact, the Mesopotamian God King Nimrod is a leader who worships fire.

Abraham somehow escapes this. In the belief of Prophet Abraham, God orders him to sacrifice his son by slaughtering him for himself. The meat of the sacrificed person was distributed to all tribe members and the meat of the victim was cooked and eaten. Today, this sacrificial tradition continues in the same way, but the only change is that now animals, not children, are sacrificed. It was essential to sacrifice a young and strong son. In the excavations carried out in the Değirmentepe mound in the Mesopotamia region, there are child graves but no adult graves. Nimrod may have committed infanticide. because he could not find a single child to sacrifice to the God of Prophet Abraham, his greatest enemy. Thus, Prophet Abraham cannot sacrifice to his god. This is the first time I am writing these theories. Abraham's tribe may have dedicated their children and babies to God. In tribal wars, the first target will be children, in order to prevent the enemy generation from continuing and leaving behind a descendant that will take revenge. This is my first time writing these. Baby and child graves also stand out in different geographies of Anatolia. Due to the lack of food and water, healthy babies are kept alive and weaker babies are killed by the family. This is also a possible possibility. When the babies reached a certain maturity, that is, when they were weaned, the baby's mother would chew the meat brought to her from the hunt and feed it to her child, who was mature enough to eat it, by taking it out of his mouth and transferring it to his mouth. So, just like other carnivorous animals. Considering that the tribe is herbivorous, this may be more comfortable for the mother because the weaned child can easily tear apart and consume a plant or a fruit with its teeth without the help of its mother. Is such a transition process possible for children?

Could such a method be followed by first feeding the weaned child with raw eggs or plants for a while until it reaches maturity where it can consume meat on its own?

As revealed in the Çayönü Mound in Anatolia, the houses were built adjacent to each other and in this way they were built separately from each other in the form of tribal houses. Social categorization based on origin, such as my tribe, your tribe, my tribe, your tribe, is very evident in this period. These houses form the basis of today's modern houses. A house consists of only one room. Parents and children live in it. There is an adjoining room where the other family lives. Next to that is another room where another family lives. In this region, cutting off the nose and ears of unchaste and unfaithful women is a common method of shaming and punishment. We can see this today in Afghanistan, where a woman named Bibi Aisha, who was abandoned after having her nose and ear cut off, was the cover photo of TIME magazine in 2010. In this geography, the tradition of cutting off the thief's hand with whichever hand he stole with is also a common practice and has a place in religions. In both Egyptian and Mesopotamian civilizations, the physician who causes the death of a patient is punished with death penalty as a deterrent.

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